

Barbie: The Performance of Reality

On How to Drink Milk Without Drinking Milk

Roger Tavares, Jul, 26, 2025.

Short essay originally published on [Substack](#).

I'm one of those people who enjoys peeling onions. Layer after layer, between one tear and another, a new discovery emerges, with more yet to come. The 2023 *Barbie* movie, directed by Greta Gerwig, gives me this exact feeling, but without the tears.

This is the kind of film that the more you watch, the more you notice. And there's one scene in particular that shows us how even a very simple thing can contain layers and layers of meaning: when Barbie drinks milk, without actually drinking it.

Frame of Barbie movie (2023)

For those who still haven't seen the film (*Shame! Shame! Shame!*), the story unfolds when Barbie has to leave Barbieland and go to the real world to solve some existential problems that have begun to emerge. Barbie lives in an idealized world where houses have no walls, the days are always perfect, and the nights are one big party. The real world, on the other hand, has walls, days have names and functions, and parties end early for those who have to work the next day, like me.

The film was heavily criticized, especially by the people who understood it the least. They went in expecting a pink world and were met with so many colors they couldn't perceive anything, not even the pink. There are moments both overt and subtle, with references ranging from *2001: A Space Odyssey* to *The Matrix*, from Barbie's history, from teenager to President, and jokes about Mattel and the corporate world. Some of these impact us more, others less, which is why it's important to watch the film more than once.

The scene I've chosen to break down here is a very simple one, but it had a profound impact on me: when Barbie has her morning milk. Early in the film, Barbie wakes up, takes her waterless shower, changes from her pajamas into a 1950s-style gingham dress, opens the refrigerator, takes out a carton of milk, pours it into a cup, and lifts the cup to her mouth as if drinking the contents. Anyone who has ever played with a doll quickly identifies with this make-believe act.

This scene repeats twice more: once shortly after, when Barbie begins to notice existential problems, like worrying about death and her feet no longer being arched; and again, toward the middle of the film, when she tries to drink real water, spills it all over herself, and acknowledges that there is usually nothing inside the cup.

As we've seen, this make-believe act is the first thing we notice in this scene, but there are many others. What else could drinking milk, without any milk in the cup, signify?

An illusion of perfection. In Barbieland, everything is performative. In fact, I believe this is one of the main concepts of the film, but I'll save that for later. In this place, everything is a very superficial representation of reality. Food and drink aren't necessary because in a fantasy world, such things are basically narrative elements.

A critique of consumerism. Barbie sells a perfect but empty lifestyle. It doesn't matter what's inside, or if there's anything inside at all, because what matters is the consumption, the gesture, the appearance, not the substance. It's performance, again.

Simplicity and complexity. In Barbieland, everything is simple. But when you get to the real world, cups need to have something in them. That substance can be hot, cold, sweet, or bitter, liquid or creamy, good or spoiled. All these possibilities make the real world complex, very different from the plastic one.

An identity crisis occurs as this scene repeats. The first time, it's normal. The second time, she realizes something is wrong. The third time, when she gets wet and says there's usually nothing inside, she has accepted that what she was doing before wasn't real, but a simulation of humanity. Guess what? Performance.

A gender critique? Yes. Absolutely. In a fantasy world, women don't need substance. Society expects them to perform their roles, as professionals, wives, and mothers, but doesn't give them the necessary conditions to do so. In the real world, Barbie discovers that these cups need to be filled with autonomy, recognition, individuality, sisterhood, emotions, and gynecologists.

Idealism. Drinking without drinking, eating without eating, having professions without working, houses without walls. The empty cup pouring imaginary milk goes beyond fantasy: it shows how Barbie's world is just an ideal. The paradox here is that when Barbie was created, she was revolutionary. Before her, dolls were always babies, and consequently, children were mothers. While Barbie initially brought reality to the world of children, they could be anything she wanted, not just a mother, she later became stuck in her own idealized world, making way for other, more contemporary dolls. It's no coincidence that the teenage character is named Sasha, one of the original Bratz dolls, who were the antithesis of Barbie: full of diversity, boldness, and attitude. At the end of the film, Barbie confirms Weird Barbie's choice—in a reference to the blue or red pill choice from *The Matrix*—and trades her high-heeled shoes, the idealized woman, for Birkenstock sandals, the real woman.

This scene of the doll drinking milk probably has several other layers, but for now, these are enough. In almost all of them, we see how the concept of performance is present.

Like any concept, Performance can be viewed from different perspectives. Probably the most visible here is that of Judith Butler, an American feminist philosopher. The most blatant example is Ken trying to perform as an alpha male, a satire of toxic masculinity, or Stereotypical Barbie discovering that her smiles and waves are just gestures of what it means to be perfect. In Barbieland, everyone is acting all the time. The Barbies with their smiles, the Kens struggling for attention, and everyone following predetermined scripts.

But the wall-less houses are also another type of performance. In these, architecture is a stage, and therefore actions are visible and regulated. For Goffman, social life is a stage where we must perform roles if we want to be accepted (did anyone else think of the series *Wednesday* just now?).

Although the film does not openly address race, performance in Fanon's view suggests that racialized people are forced to perform identities that do not represent them, like Black people who straighten their hair to belong in white environments. In Barbieland, there is no diversity. The only blonde Barbie besides the protagonist, Weird Barbie, has to occupy the role of a mysterious oracle where her "deformities" are respected. The performance here is not in what is shown, but in what is deliberately omitted or segregated to maintain the "perfection" of the spectacle.

Guy Debord and his *Society of the Spectacle* could not be left out, as in his view, life is an accumulation of performances mediated by commodities. Mattel shamelessly redefines its revolutionary, feminist product and transforms it into a means to sell accessories, like clothes and careers, and more dolls.

But I will end with the most radical performance: that of art. More specifically, that of Marina Abramović, which is radically different from the previous ones. Here, performance is not about social masks or gender scripts, but an act of war against one's own limits. In this case, the performance is artistic, and the artist's body is the medium for questioning boundaries. It is therefore a conscious and extreme act. The artist donates their body to the performance. The body is both instrument and message.

When Barbie accepts the human condition, she accepts that her body now suffers, fatigues, and ages. Barbie abandons her idealized, plastic body and now possesses a body that is controlled by the state, monitored by medicine, and shaped by industry. A body that bleeds, that desires and is desired. The doll becomes a woman, the ideal becomes material, the eternal perishes, and in an extreme act, she decides to stop being a Barbie.